

Automatic Speech Recognition: Comparing Hidden Markov Model, Artificial Neural Network
and Hybrid ANN/HMM

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Abstract

“Speech is a non-stationary process, but it is assumed to be quasistationary” (Bourlard & Morgan, 2012). Automatic Speech Recognition has been the most researched topic in speech processing in the last few decades (Trentin & Gori, 2001b). Despite the advancements made over the past few decades, automatic speech recognition (ASR) is still a difficult task. Systems for recognition in particular based on hidden Markov models (HMMs) are effective in many situations, but they do suffer from certain significant drawbacks that restrict the use of ASR technology in real-world settings (Rabiner & Juang, 1992). With the advent of artificial neural networks (ANN) as an alternative paradigm for ASR, efforts were made to get over these restrictions, but ANN failed to handle lengthy time-sequences of speech signals. By integrating HMMs and ANNs into a single, hybrid design, some academics started investigating a new research topic between the end of the 1980s and the beginning of the 1990s.

This report explains the Automatic Speech Recognition system, examines its limitations and compares three speech models: Hidden Markov Model, Artificial Neural Network and hybrid ANN/HMM based on their performance based on Speech Event Detection (SED). This report further compares the Event Error Rates (EER) of the two speech recognition models and also examines the HMM and ANN hybrid model.

Keywords: Automatic Speech Recognition, Hidden Markov Model, Artificial Neural Network

Introduction

The Automatic Speech Recognition(ASR) system converts spoken language into written text and it can be used for a variety of things, including voice assistants, dictation programs, and language translation (Papers With Code - Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), n.d.). Artificial neural networks (ANNs) and hidden markov models (HMMs) are two of the most often used ASR methods. This report aims to compare two of the ASR models i.e.,Hidden Markov Model(HMM) and Transformer Model and discuss their strengths and limitations.

In recent years, interest in Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) has grown significantly. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Hidden Markov Models (HMM), and even hybrid systems like ANN are just a few of the many various techniques that have been defined for speech recognition and today speech recognition is still a very challenging issue (Imam & Al-Akaidi, 2006).

According to Bourlard and Morgan (2012) in their book titled ‘Connectionist Speech Recognition: A Hybrid Approach’ state that, the predominant technological strategies for speech recognition systems rely on pattern matching of statistical representations of the acoustic speech signal, like HMM full word and subword models. However, despite the fact that ASR has made significant strides in recent years, the typical vocabulary size is still quite small and the performance of the resulting systems is still not on par with that of humans.

Over the past few decades, the most researched area in speech processing has been Automatic Speech Recognition(ASR). It can be defined broadly as the challenge of identifying (not comprehending) the words from a particular lexicon that are spoken by a speaker while relying just on the data present in the spoken speech signal and on prior knowledge of the problem area(Trentin & Gori, 2001).

Limitations in Current ASR Systems

In Bourlard and Morgan's (2012) book titled 'Connectionist Speech Recognition: A Hybrid Approach', they explain some of the limitations in the ASRs. They are:

- **Similar Phonetic Structure.** Words with completely distinct meanings can share a lot of similarities in their phonetic structure. Furthermore, words used in connected speech are pronounced very differently, frequently omitting phonemes that are explicitly stated in isolated words.
- **No restrictions on Sentence Lengths.** Since there is no limit on sentence length, there are an infinite number of sentences that can be spoken, and even a fictitious limit allows for an enormous variety of word combinations. Each of these combinations has an impact on how words and phonemes are pronounced (particularly because of contextual influences from nearby sounds).
- **Variability of the speech acoustic and variation of additive and convolutional noise.** The speech spectrum can significantly alter due to changes in the speech collection environment, such as changes in the room's acoustics, the channel's spectral properties, or the microphone's response, all of which can significantly impair recognizer performance. The heterogeneity for dialect, speaking pace, and other talker-dependent features when a system must be speaker-independent makes the task more challenging and often doubles the error rate, even within the same dialect or accent group.

Bourlard and Morgan(2012) suggest that, to achieve high recognition performance, efforts should be made to improve the speech recognizer. With task-restricted grammar, such systems can undoubtedly provide some incredibly spectacular results in the lab; 95–98% accuracy rates

for the recognition of 1000 words in continuous speech have been recorded (Boulevard and Morgan, 2012).

Hidden Markov Model

The Hidden Markov Model (HMM) has been developed in the context of a long history of pattern recognition technology (Boulevard and Morgan, 2012).

“The HMM is called ‘hidden’ because the sequence of states is not directly observable, but affects the observed sequence of events.” (Boulevard and Morgan, 2012)

The probability maximization criterion is used in HMMs to make judgments at the acoustic level; the HMM that best matches the current input pattern is chosen. Therefore, all evidence seems to point to HMMs' success in event-based detection as well. On the other hand, event detection primarily relies on a classification problem, which might be better addressed via a discriminative technique (Da Silva Teixeira et al., 2008).

Refer to Appendix for the Python code and results for Part-Of-Speech tagging with HMM.

Over the past few years, hidden Markov models (HMMs) have gained popularity for use in speech recognition (Rabiner & Juang, 1992). Researchers shifted from conventional simple models in the 1980s to more intricate statistical models like Hidden Markov Models (HMMs). Despite being superior to other models, HMMs have a number of drawbacks and issues, due to which, some researchers resorted to Artificial Neural Networks(ANNs).

Artificial Neural Network

Da Silva Teixeira et al. (2008) explain ANNs as a significant class of discriminative methods that are excellent at classifying issues. Our objective is perfectly provided by their capacity to be used as a detecting mechanism that gains knowledge from seen data.

Additionally, given that statistical distributions can change with each event class, its

discriminative learning capability—where there is no need to make assumptions about the class statistical distributions—is a remarkable feature.

There are many justifications for utilizing ANNs for ASR, some of which are dubious or not exclusive to ANNs, while others are especially compelling for ASR. Based on Bourlard and Morgan's (2012) explanation, following are the advantages of using ANN:

- **Provide discriminant-based learning.** Models are trained to reduce error rates while increasing the gap between the ideal model and its competitors.
- **Flexible Architecture.** They feature an extremely adaptable architecture that makes it simple to take into account contextual inputs and feedback.
- **Parallel and Regular Structures.** ANNs are typically highly parallel and regular structures, which makes them especially amenable to high-performance architectures and hardware implementations.
- **Capable of incorporating multiple constraints.** Features do not have to be treated independently because they can combine many constraints and identify the best combinations of constraints for categorization. Unlike what is typically required in normal HMMs, no strong assumptions regarding the statistical distributions of the input features are necessary.

According to Rabiner and Juang (1992), despite the emergence of the Time Delay Neural Network (TDNN) and related models and the fact that neural networks are effective classifiers that can quickly generalize, ANN's have not been able to offer a comprehensive framework for ASR that would take into account lengthy sequences of auditory information. Due to this, hybrid ANN/HMM and ANN/DPASR models first appeared in the early 1990s.

Method

Information for this research report was sourced from various Secondary sources. The secondary sources used to gather the data for this research are all given in the Reference List. Additionally useful were the data and experiments from Da Silva Teixeira et al. (2008) publications. There have been several research studies on using Hidden Markov Model and Artificial Neural Network focused on detecting events but there are no studies comparing the performance of these models to the best of my knowledge. This study offers a broad overview of the subject but does not review all of the relevant literature.

Event-Based System description

Da Silva Teixeira et al. (2008) in their study propose a front-end which performs utterance segmentation in terms of a sequence of events over time and four attributes to be detected were defined: silence, frication, stops and sonorancy, in such a way that the output signal of the proposed front-end is a segmented signal in terms of four broad classes: silences,fricatives, stops and sonorants. The TIMIT database was used to carry out the experiment.

TIMIT is a widely used speech corpus for speech recognition and related tasks. TIMIT is an audio library of spoken English sentences delivered by 630 people from different American areas and dialects. The corpus includes recordings of speakers who are both male and female, as well as speakers of various ages and ethnicities. The experiment conducted by Da Sila Teixeira et al. (2008) used TIMIT database not only because it provides manually segmented phoneme boundaries but also because it is widely used and thus allowing to compare results with other works.

According to the phoneme sets shown in Table 1, the 61 TIMIT-labeled phones were classified into 4 broad classes (sonorant, fricative, stop, and silent). Correctness (Corr), Accuracy (Acc), and Event Error Rate (EER) are measured for the performance (Da Silva Teixeira et al., 2008).

Table 1: 61 TIMIT-labeled phones division into 4 broad classes of events

Broad classes	TIMIT-labeled phones
Fricatives	z, zh, s, sh, jh, ch, th, f, dh ,v
Silences	h#, epi, pau, bcl, dcl, gcl, pcl, kcl, tcl, q
Stops	b, d, g, p, t, k
Sonorants	dx, hv, l, m, n, ng, nx, r, w, y, hh, aa, ae, ah, ao, aw, ax-h, axr, ay, ax,eh, el, em, en, eng, er,ey, ih, ix, iy, ow, oy, uh, uw, ux

Findings

Based on Da Silva Teixeira et al. (2008) in their study, following are the findings:

Hidden Markov Model

HMM are used heavily for speech recognition. Their success depends on their capacity to model the speech signal's acoustic and temporal characteristics. HMMs model the temporal evolution of the speech signal while statistically expressing the speech signal. Sonorant, stop, fricative, and silence acoustic models were created using HTK3.4 in order to create an HMM-based event classifier. Table 2 summarizes the HMM Classifier results obtained by Da Silva Teixeira et al. (2008).

HMM Classifier	Correctness	Accuracy	Number of training parameters
1 Gaussian mixture	88.47%	73.14%	979
8 Gaussian mixtures	89.36%	77.57%	7615

Table 2: HMM Classifier's Results

Da Silva Teixeira et al. (2008) observe that, although HMMs perform exceptionally well in speech recognition applications, the training maximum likelihood criterion has some drawbacks. This criterion increases the likelihood that a specific model will produce the observation sequence, but it does not reduce the likelihood that other models will produce the same sequence. The distribution of the competing speech classes is unknown to any HMM model, even if it has the right distribution for the associated speech (Da Silva Teixeira et al., 2008). Due to these drawbacks, other training methods like ANN and hybrid models such as ANN/HMM, which base their training on comparisons of likelihood scores estimated for speech units, have emerged.

Artificial Neural Network

ANNs are an important group of discriminative techniques (Da Silva Teixeira et al., 2008). They are appropriate for classification issues since they are taught using a global discriminative criterion. Each input vector is given a discriminative weight by the ANN, which results in frame-level discrimination between the involved classes.

According to Da Silva Teixeira et al., (2008), although ANN architectures perform well in terms of frame error rate—again unlike HMMs—they do have some drawbacks. Despite not requiring any assumptions about the underlying statistical properties of the input data, ANNs do have some limitations (Da Silva Teixeira et al., 2008). The study also states that ANNs were initially static classifiers which makes it a major drawback. They have to cope with the duration variability of speech units in ASR because they do not naturally model the temporal evolution of data and as a potential fix for this issue, the idea of a hybrid system (ANN/HMM) developed (Da Silva Teixeira et al., 2008). The Hybrid ANN/HMM Speech Event Detector's concept is to integrate HMMs and ANN into a single system to benefit from the finest aspects of both methodologies.

Hybrid ASR(ANN/HMM)

Standard HMMs have a cohesive and consolidated theoretical foundation, but hybrid ANN/HMM systems are a more new study area (Trentin & Gori, 2001c). According to the study published by Da Silva Teixeira et al., (2008), the hybrid ANN/HMM system outperformed the other models; accuracy increased to 76.16%, and correctness to 81.9%, improvements of 11.2% in EER were made as compared to the HMM event detector and has a low number of training parameter.

Conclusion

Automatic speech recognition is challenging because of how human speech is produced, which is unpredictable and sequential. In this research report, three systems were introduced for speech event detection. The first system is based on a traditional HMM. According to the study conducted and published by Da Silva Teixeira et al., in 2008, both methods outperform the traditional HMM results with respective improvements of 3% and 6% were achieved in EER; another tested approach was based on a hybrid single layer MLP/HMM. This last approach achieves notable results. Improvements of 11% and 8% were found in comparison with the HMM and hybrid SVM/HMM event detector, respectively. The results of the study are summarized in Table 3. The paper has compared the performance of the three classifiers, showing the strengths and weaknesses of each (Da Silva Teixeira et al., in 2008). Despite an English database being used for testing the study believes that similar results can be achieved applying the methods to other languages, since the detected events are common to all languages (Da Silva Teixeira et al., in 2008).

Table 3: Performance Results

Performance	% Corr	% Acc	% EER	Number of training parameters	Improvements(%)		
HMM Event Detector (1mix)	88.47	73.14	26.86	979			
Hybrid ANN/HMM	81.93	76.16	23.84	983	11.2	8.3	5.5
HMM Event Detector (8 mix)	89.36	77.57	22.43	7615			
Hybrid ANN/HMM	87.12	80.17	19.83	7513	11.6		

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Appendix

As a part of the Research Report, to understand the POS for HMM, a python code with NLTK packages was used based on the following GitHub link:

<https://gist.github.com/blumonkey/007955ec2f67119e0909>

```
# Import the toolkit and tags

import nltk

from nltk.corpus import treebank

# Train data - pretagged

train_data = treebank.tagged_sents)[:3000]

print(train_data[0])

# Import HMM module

from nltk.tag import hmm

# Setup a trainer with default(None) values

# And train with the data

trainer = hmm.HiddenMarkovModelTrainer()

tagger = nltk.HiddenMarkovModelTagger.train(train_data)

# tagger = trainer.train_supervised(train_data)

print(tagger)

# Prints the basic data about the tagger

print(tagger.tag("Today is a good day ".split()))

print(tagger.tag("Joe met Joanne in Delhi ".split()))

print(tagger.tag("Chicago is the birthplace of Ginny".split()))
```

""

Output in order (Notice some tags are wrong :/):

[('Today', u'NN'), ('is', u'VBZ'), ('a', u'DT'), ('good', u'JJ'), ('day', u'NN'), (',', u'.')]]

[('Joe', u'NNP'), ('met', u'VBD'), ('Joanne', u'NNP'), ('in', u'IN'), ('Delhi', u'NNP'), (',', u'NNP')]]

[('Chicago', u'NNP'), ('is', u'VBZ'), ('the', u'DT'), ('birthplace', u'NNP'), ('of', u'NNP'), ('Ginny', u'NNP')]]

""

Result:

[('Pierre', 'NNP'), ('Vinken', 'NNP'), (',', ','), ('61', 'CD'), ('years', 'NNS'), ('old', 'JJ'), (',', ','), ('will', 'MD'), ('join', 'VB'), ('the', 'DT'), ('board', 'NN'), ('as', 'IN'), ('a', 'DT'), ('nonexecutive', 'JJ'), ('director', 'NN'), ('Nov.', 'NNP'), ('29', 'CD'), (',', ',')]]

<HiddenMarkovModelTagger 46 states and 10779 output symbols>

[('Today', 'NN'), ('is', 'VBZ'), ('a', 'DT'), ('good', 'JJ'), ('day', 'NN'), (',', ',')]]

[('Joe', 'NNP'), ('met', 'VBD'), ('Joanne', '-NONE-'), ('in', 'IN'), ('Delhi', 'NNS'), (',', ',')]]

[('Chicago', 'NNP'), ('is', 'VBZ'), ('the', 'DT'), ('birthplace', 'NN'), ('of', 'IN'), ('Ginny', 'DT')]]

"\nOutput in order (Notice some tags are wrong :/):\n[('Today', u'NN'), ('is', u'VBZ'), ('a', u'DT'), ('good', u'JJ'), ('day', u'NN'), (',', u'.')] \n[('Joe', u'NNP'), ('met', u'VBD'), ('Joanne', u'NNP'), ('in', u'IN'), ('Delhi', u'NNP'), (',', u'NNP')] \n[('Chicago', u'NNP'), ('is', u'VBZ'), ('the', u'DT'), ('birthplace', u'NNP'), ('of', u'NNP'), ('Ginny', u'NNP')] \n"

Total Word Count: 2700